

PHYSICAL AMBIENCE AND CUSTOMER BEHAVIOUR IN SELECTED MICROFINANCE BANKS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract: The competitive landscape in the Microfinance Banking Industry has accentuated the need for effective physical ambience strategy in the marketing of bank services. The objective of this study was to examine the effect of physical ambience on the behavior of Microfinance Banks customers in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, primary data were obtained using the questionnaire. The researchers adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 369 respondents drawn from the banks' customer base. A total number of 346 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 98.6 percent. Simple Regression Model (SRM) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that colour, temperature, design and layout had significant influence on customer behavior in Microfinance Banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Thus, we recommended that managers of Microfinance Banks should design their business environment in order to produce specific value perceptions in the customer as well as create an outstanding experience that is viable to attract and retain the banks existing and potential customers

Keywords: Physical ambience, Atmospherics. Consumer behavior, Microfinance bank

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Research indicates that the business environment has a significant impact on the purchasing behavior of bank consumers. For microfinance banks, the physical atmosphere plays a crucial role in creating an exceptional experience that can attract and retain both current and potential customers. Elements like sound, temperature, scent, colors, noise, spatial arrangement, lighting, music, signage, and dress code, collectively referred to as physical ambience variables, can intentionally or unintentionally influence various aspects of customer behavior during their service interactions (Jhakini, 2016).

Ambiance, which is synonymous with atmosphere, is defined as the mood or environment within the bank (source: [vocabulary.com](https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary)>dictionary). Therefore, physical ambience can be described as the emotional atmosphere associated with a specific place, person, or thing. These atmospheres are carefully planned and designed in a way that stimulates customers of microfinance banks to lean towards purchasing the bank's particular service or product (Kotler and Armstrong, 2013). It involves the ability to shape the buying environment of microfinance banks to evoke specific emotions in their customers, ultimately increasing the likelihood of purchase (Kotler and

Armstrong, 2013). Consequently, microfinance banks are structured and organized to convey trust and other qualities highly valued by their customers (Kotler and Armstrong, 2013). The pleasant atmosphere within the bank can create a positive experience for customers, directly influencing their intention to make a purchase and aiding in their decision-making process (Munshi, 2018)

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Research findings have shown that the failure of microfinance banks to strategically create and utilize their physical environment, including elements like sound, temperature, aroma, colors, noise, spatial arrangement, lighting, signage, symbols, dress code, and architectural design, as a means to gain a competitive edge and shape their customers' inclination towards purchasing specific services has negatively impacted public trust in these banks, consequently affecting customer buying behavior (Yang, Cao, Ye, and Shi, 2022; Ndengane, Mason, and Mutize, 2021).

Regrettably, numerous studies, such as those by Paz and Delgado (2021), Roberts and Grassi (2021), Acha (2012), Sabrina (2014), Munshi (2018), and Turley and Milliman (2000), have investigated various aspects of microfinance bank operations, yet very limited attention has been directed towards exploring the relationship between physical ambiance and consumer behavior in microfinance banks, especially in developing economies like Nigeria. Additionally, many research endeavors in the realm of financial institutions have predominantly centered on deposit money banks, with minimal or no focus on microfinance banks, particularly in Nigeria (Patil et al., 2021). It is within this context that we aim to examine the impact of physical ambiance on consumer behavior, with specific emphasis on microfinance banks located in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The glaring knowledge gap in this area served as the primary motivation for conducting this study.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of physical ambiance on customer behavior in selected microfinance in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives therefore include to;

- Determine the influence of temperature on customer behavior in microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- Examine the influence of colour on customer behavior in microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.
- Examine the influence of layout and designs on customer behavior in microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

This study attempts to provide answers to the following research questions.

1. What is the influence of temperature on customer behavior in microfinance banks?
2. What is the influence of colour on customer behavior in microfinance banks?
3. What is the influence of layout and design on customer behavior in microfinance banks?

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

The following null hypotheses were postulated to guide the study:

1. Temperature does not significantly influence customer behavior in microfinance banks.
2. Colours does not significantly influence customer behavior in microfinance banks
3. Layout and Designs does not significantly influence customer behavior in microfinance banks

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study holds significant importance for various stakeholders, including government officials, bank regulators, bank managers, investors, academics, and others. It is poised to make substantial contributions to the business landscape in multiple dimensions, such as increasing sales volumes, improving return on investment, and maintaining a positive reputation.

By pinpointing the strengths of select microfinance banks, it can play a pivotal role in rebuilding public trust in these institutions, thereby fostering positive social change within our society. Furthermore, this research will provide invaluable insights into the challenges faced by microfinance banks, shedding light on the hurdles they encounter. This knowledge can then be used to devise effective solutions to address these challenges, both by bank managers and government authorities. Ultimately, this study has the potential to guide efforts aimed at enhancing the reputation and performance of microfinance banks in the state.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The Scope of the study covered the following three central aspects

Content Scope: The content scope of this study covers the physical ambience variables used by microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State such as temperature, colours, layout/designs and the consumer behavior. It also covers the concepts on physical ambience and consumer behavior, physical ambience tools as related to consumer behavior. This study was domicile in strategic and service marketing.

Geographical Scope: The geographical scope of the study was in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State located at the South South region of Nigeria.

Unit of Analysis: The Unit of analysis of this study involved customers of the selected microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Atmospheric

Atmospherics, as a concept, pertains to the emotional experience of the buying process that is not immediately visible (Munshi, 2018). It involves shaping the physical space of microfinance banks in a way that influences the emotions and behaviors of their customers.

Atmospherics encompasses the physical aspects of the bank's environment, including the design of the building, layout, interior space, aisle arrangement, floor and wall textures, colors, scents, shapes, symbols, temperature, and sounds experienced by customers. It plays a crucial role for microfinance banks because it transforms space and molds consumer behavior. The altered environment affects consumers by engaging their senses, influencing their perceptions and attitudes, ultimately aiming to elicit specific desired reactions from customers.

Patil et al. (2021) conducted a study on the impact of store atmosphere on consumer buying behavior in Bengaluru

retail stores. Their findings indicated that various elements of atmosphere have significant effects on customer behavior. For instance, pleasant music, good lighting, clear layout and display, appealing business graphics, coworkers' recommendations, store location, convenient parking, waiting time, promotions, and visual merchandising all played distinct roles in motivating consumers to visit and purchase from stores.

Ndengane et al. (2021) also revealed that store atmosphere variables like cleanliness, lighting, floor advertisements, music, employee appearance, and efficient service substantially contribute to shaping customers' feelings, mood, the store's positive image, the time spent in the store, and the likelihood of customers returning for future visits.

2.1.2 The Concept of Consumer Behaviour

Given the intense competition in the microfinance sector, the success of mobilizing savings, attracting, and retaining customer's hinges on a bank's ability to meet customer needs and understand their buying behavior (Munshi, 2018). Consumer behavior encompasses how individuals search for, use, evaluate, and dispose of goods and services they believe will fulfill their needs (Munshi, 2018).

Pride and Ferrel (1985) define consumer buying as the ultimate act in the spectrum of consumer behavior. Boone and Kurtz (1980) view it as the individual actions directly related to acquiring and using economic goods and services, including the decision-making process that precedes and influences these actions.

Kotler and Keller (2011) emphasize that microfinance banks can gain a competitive advantage by comprehending their customers' buying behavior and how they select service products. They suggest that banks can use this knowledge to formulate strategies that offer the right services to the right customer segments, aligning effectively with their needs and desires.

In a study by Yang et al. (2022), the focus was on the impact of interface design and live-streaming atmosphere on consumer impulse buying behavior. The research delved into the effect of human-computer interaction on consumers' inner states, such as visual appeal, perceived arousal, and consumer engagement. The results highlighted that interface design and the live atmosphere significantly and positively influenced consumers' impulse purchasing behavior, with these effects being mediated by factors like visual appeal, perceived arousal, and consumer engagement to varying degrees.

2.1.3 Relation between Physical Ambience Variables; Temperature, Colours, Layout/ Designs and Consumer Behaviour

Today's marketers are keen on understanding why certain customers choose a particular microfinance bank, why others do not, and how potential customers who haven't patronized the bank can be persuaded to become actual customers (Anyanmu, 2013).

The temperature within microfinance banks significantly impacts consumers' intentions to purchase the bank's service products. Inappropriate temperatures, whether too low or too high, can create negative feelings among customers, leading to dissatisfaction. This dissatisfaction results in customers spending less time in the banking hall and potentially spreading negative word-of-mouth (Lam, 2001).

Hussain and Ali (2015) conducted a study on the effect of store atmosphere on consumer purchase intention.

Their findings showed that atmospheric variables such as cleanliness, scent, lighting, and display/layout had a positive influence on consumer purchase intention. However, music, color, and temperature had minimal impact on consumers' purchase intentions.

Color plays a role in influencing consumer attitudes and behavior (Benat and Wandebori, 2012). Different colors can evoke specific feelings, stimulate memories, and influence perception (Hussain and Ali, 2015). For example, red environments are often seen as unpleasant and tense, while blue and green environments are perceived as more positive and calming (Yulsei, 2009).

The physical design and layout of microfinance banks can also significantly influence customer buying behavior (Word, 2020; Ndengane et al., 2021). Elements like space design, traffic flow, workstations, equipment placement, cash register placement, waiting areas, furniture, artwork, bank size, banking hall size, parking facilities, and cashier placement can all impact customer experiences. A well-designed bank encourages customers to stay longer and have a more pleasant and enjoyable experience (Patil et al., 2021). Easy access from the outside and simple navigation inside the bank contribute to this positive experience. In this direction the relationship between physical ambience variables and consumer behavior of microfinance banks are shown in figure 2.1

Figure 2.1: schematic model of the relationship between physical ambience variables and consumer behavior

Source: Author's operational framework

2.2 Theoretical Framework

In this section, three major theories were considered relevant for this study. They include: **The Stimulus**

FIGURE 2.2: SOR MODEL

Organism Response theory propounded by Woodworth (1929) SOURCE: Mehrabian and Russel (1974)

The Stimulus-Response (S.O.R) model is a valuable tool for marketers in comprehending consumer buying behavior. It centers on the idea that a buyer's consciousness is shaped by environmental and marketing stimuli, with the decision process and customer characteristics playing pivotal roles in forming successful purchasing decisions.

Mehrabian and Russell (1974) introduced three distinct dimensions related to emotional responses to the environment:

1. Pleasure: This dimension measures the level of pleasure based on verbal judgments tied to emotions like joy, satisfaction, and happiness in various situations.
2. Arousal: Arousal is gauged through verbal judgments and relates to the level of activity or alertness in an individual or situation. For instance, it measures how active someone is feeling based on their verbal expressions.
3. Dominance: Dominance is predicted using the emotions or feelings expressed by respondents. It relates to the willingness of individuals to assert themselves or take charge in a given situational environmental context.

These three dimensions suggest that each individual can be influenced by emotional conditions depending on their specific environment. The S.O.R theory posits that environmental stimuli (S) directly affect the cognitive and affective states (O) of individuals, which, in turn, influence their behavior (R). This theory is widely applied to explain the consumer decision-making process and to gain insights into its fundamental mechanisms.

The Engel-Kollat-Blackwell Model (EKB) propounded by Blackwell, R., Kollat, D. and Engel, J. (1968)

This is one of the most respected views of consumer behavior. The model describe consumer behavior as a decision process which involves five activities such as;

1. Problem Recognition
2. Informative Search
3. Alternative evaluation
4. Choice and
5. Post Purchase Evaluation

This model view the consumer as a rational being capable of reacting to certain influences or factors and making reasonable decisions based on such influences on him.

❖ **Recognition of Need or Problem:** The process begins when a consumer recognizes a need or problem in their life that could be addressed by purchasing a particular product or service. This need or problem serves as the motivation for the consumer to start the decision-making journey.

❖ **Search for Information:** Once the need is recognized, the consumer actively seeks information on how to satisfy that need. This information can come from various sources, including personal experiences, recommendations, online research, and marketing materials.

❖ **Alternative Evaluation:** With the necessary information at hand, the consumer evaluates different alternatives available in the market. This evaluation involves considering various factors such as attitudes, personality, motivation, past experiences, opinions from reference groups (e.g., friends and family), cultural influences, and the physical environment of the purchase location. All these factors play a role in shaping the consumer's decision.

❖ **Choice:** After thorough evaluation, the consumer makes the final decision regarding whether to make a purchase or not. If the decision is to buy, the consumer selects a specific alternative from the available choices.

❖ **Post-Purchase Evaluation:** Following the purchase, the consumer evaluates the wisdom of their decision. This post-purchase evaluation is a learning experience that can impact future purchase decisions. Positive experiences may lead to repeat purchases and the formation of habits. Conversely, negative experiences may result in more extensive research and consideration in future buying decisions. The consumer may either give an unsatisfactory product a second chance or exclude it from consideration altogether in future purchases.

Understanding this consumer decision-making process is crucial for businesses and marketers as it helps them tailor their marketing strategies to influence each stage effectively and meet the needs and expectations of consumers.

NICOSIA MODEL PROPOUNDED BY NICOSIA, F. M. (1966)

Figure 2.3: Nicosia model

Source: Schiffman and Kanuk, 2003

The Nicosia model is a conceptual framework that focuses on the dynamic relationship between a firm and its potential consumers. It employs flowcharts to depict the fundamental elements of the decision-making process and illustrates the interaction between the firm's efforts to influence consumers and how consumers, in turn, seek to influence the firm.

This model is interactive and circular in design, highlighting how the firm attempts to influence consumers and how consumers, through their actions or inactions, also influence the firm.

The consumer decision process in the Nicosia model consists of four interconnected fields, where the output from each field becomes an input into the subsequent one:

Field One (Source of Message to Consumer Attributes): This field encompasses the message source, which includes advertising messages from the business firm, as well as aspects of the firm's marketing environment and marketing communication efforts that influence consumer attitudes. The message from the firm in Field One serves as input to the "consumer's space," which is composed of psychological attitudes.

Field Two (Search and Evaluation): In this field, consumers process the message received and accepted from Field One. They engage in the process of searching for information and evaluating the product or service

mentioned in the message, as well as considering alternatives within the same product category. The actions in this field may or may not lead to motivation to purchase, but when motivation occurs, it serves as input into Field Three.

Field Three (Purchase): This field focuses on the actual act of purchase. It involves transforming the consumer's intention to purchase into a purchase decision. The consumer's motivation toward the firm's brand results in a decision and, ultimately, the actual purchase of the product or service from a specific firm.

Field Four (Feedback): The final field deals with feedback. It involves two main types of feedback resulting from the purchase experience. First, there is feedback to the firm in the form of sales data. Second, there is feedback to the consumer in the form of their experience, which could be satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The consumer's experience with the product influences their individual attitudes and tendencies toward the firm's future messages. The Nicosia model provides a structured way of understanding the complex dynamics of consumer decision-making and the ongoing relationship between firms and consumers. It emphasizes the feedback loop between the two parties, recognizing that consumer experiences and attitudes can shape future interactions and decisions.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

This section is concerned with the review of the studies which were considered to be relevant, accordingly 10 studies were reviewed.

2.3.1 Ndengane, Mason and Mutize (2021): Conducted a Study on the Influence of Store Atmospherics on Customers' Satisfaction at Selected South Africa Retail Outlets

They utilized correlation and factor analysis as methods for data analysis. The results of the study revealed a positive connection between the independent variables (Cleanliness, lighting, music, floor advertisements, efficient employee service, employee appearance) and the dependent variables (Positive store image, pleasant mood, time spent in the store, intention to revisit the store). Their conclusion was that customers are positively influenced by innovative environmental cues and can be enticed by the shopping environment. They suggested that retailers should strive to create an attractive shopping experience for customers, as this would contribute to the growth and profitability of retail businesses, as well as enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. Furthermore, they recommended that retailers pay close attention to ambient, design, and social factors, as effective management of these aspects can enhance the overall shopping experience. To remain competitive in the market, retailers should consistently review and revitalize their strategies for creating a store atmosphere.

2.3.2 Patil, et al, (2021): Studied the Effect of Store Atmosphere on Consumer Buying Behavior in Beragaluru Retail Stores

They aimed to explore how atmospheric factors like crowd density, store floor space, and product assortment affect consumer buying behavior. They employed the chi-square test for data analysis and discovered that the retail environment had an impact on several aspects of a shopper's cognitive processes, including attention, interpretation, categorization, and information processing. Additionally, they identified a significant connection between consumer visits and the influence of the retail ambiance. In conclusion, they found that each component of the store environment played a role in shaping consumer behavior and had a positive impact. Their

recommendations included a focus on both product quality and the in-store environment, along with efforts to stimulate consumers' quality awareness and curiosity to enhance customer loyalty. Furthermore, they suggested the establishment of touchless cash points to promote contactless payments.

2.3.3 Yang, et al (2022): In their Study on the Effects of Interface Design and Live Atmosphere on Consumers' Impulse-Buying Behavior from the Perspective of Human Computer Interaction

Yang et al conducted a study examining how interface design and the live-streaming atmosphere influence consumers' impulse buying behavior. They also explored the impact of human-computer interaction on consumers' inner states, including visual appeal, perceptual arousal, and consumer engagement. To analyze their data, they employed partial least squares structural equation modeling. The study's findings revealed that consumers' visual appeal, perceived arousal, and engagement act as mediators in the relationships between interface design, live atmosphere, and impulse purchases. In summary, Yang et al. concluded that both interface design and the live-streaming atmosphere have a significant and positive impact on consumers' impulse buying behavior. These effects were found to be moderated to varying degrees by visual appeal, perceived arousal, and consumer engagement. As recommendations, they suggested that for the sustainability of the live-streaming economy, live streaming platforms should focus on designing appealing live-streaming interfaces, creating a pleasant live-streaming atmosphere, and enhancing consumers' positive emotions while preventing irrational purchasing behavior. These efforts can help stakeholders promote the sustainability of e-commerce live streaming in practice.

2.3.4 Hussain and Ali (2015): Effect of Store Atmosphere on Consumer Purchase intention

Hussain and Ali conducted a study in Karachi, Pakistan, to examine how the in-store atmosphere affects consumer purchase intentions in international retail chain outlets. They employed regression analysis to analyze their data and made several key observations. Their findings indicated that certain atmospheric variables, specifically cleanliness, scent, lighting, and display layout, had a notably positive impact on consumers' purchase intentions. However, they found that music and color had relatively insignificant effects on consumer purchase intentions. Furthermore, temperature appeared to have almost no influence on consumers' purchase intentions. In conclusion, Hussain and Ali highlighted that store atmosphere variables, such as cleanliness, scent, lighting, and display/layout, had a significant and positive influence on consumers' intentions to make a purchase. As a recommendation, they suggested that the managers and owners of retail chain outlets should focus on enhancing the effective use of lighting, cleanliness, scent, and color within their stores to align with the attitudes and perceptions of their customers. This adjustment could help improve the overall shopping experience and drive purchase intentions.

2.3.5 Holmes (2007): The Influence of Atmospheric on Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality, Merchandise Price and Merchandise Quality Influencing Behavioral Intentions. A Retailing Study of Outlet Malls

He investigated how the atmosphere within an outlet mall affects how consumers perceive the quality of service, merchandise pricing, merchandise quality, and how these factors influence their behavioral intentions. The

research employed both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study's results indicated that atmospheric factors and the human element of crowding were connected to how consumers perceive the service quality, merchandise pricing, and merchandise quality within the outlet mall. However, the study found no significant relationship between atmospheric factors, crowding, and consumer behavioral intentions at the mall. Furthermore, the findings revealed a significant link between consumers' perception of service quality and their behavioral intentions. Similarly, there was a significant association between consumers' perception of merchandise quality in the outlet mall and their behavioral intentions. In conclusion, the research pointed out that the external ambiance of the mall and perceptions of crowding have an impact on how consumers perceive the service quality, merchandise pricing, and merchandise quality. As a recommendation, the study suggests that mall managers should concentrate on improving the external mall environment and implement crowd management measures to foster positive perceptions among consumers.

2.3.6 Chen and Hsieh (2011): Studied the Effect of Atmosphere on Customer Perceptions and Customer Behavior Responses in Chain Store Supermarkets

They employed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for data analysis, and their study yielded the following findings:

1. Customer perception of store atmospheres in the chain store supermarket encompassed six factors grouped into three categories: design factors, ambient factors (including intangible aspects and visual stimuli), and social factors (encompassing the image of service personnel, image of other customers, and environmental crowding).
2. Store atmospheric factors exhibited a significant positive correlation with customer approach behavior, with design factors exerting the most significant impact among all factors. These store atmospheric factors not only influenced customer emotions but also shaped customers' cognitive assessments of products and services. Consequently, customers' cognitive evaluations and emotional responses significantly influenced their approach behavior.
3. Customers with varying characteristics, such as different shopping pricing preferences, time urgency, and environmental familiarity, had a notable impact on customer perceptions and behavior. The researchers concluded that store atmospheric factors, including intangible elements and visual stimuli such as music/noise, temperature, lighting, and colors, significantly influenced customer perceptions and behavioral responses in chain store supermarkets. These factors contributed to customers maintaining active and positive emotions, leading to pleasant experiences.

As a recommendation, they advised supermarket managers to design the overall layout of the supermarket environment to create a relaxed and anxiety-free atmosphere, ensuring that customers consistently experience positive emotions. This approach can contribute to customer satisfaction and loyalty.

2.3.7 Munshi (2018): Impact of Store Atmospherics on Consumer Buying Behavior at D-Mart Store

Munshi conducted a study to explore how specific store environment factors, including product variety, store layout, and crowd levels, affected consumer purchasing patterns at D-Mart Stores in Vadodara. The research utilized regression analysis for data examination and made the following observations:

The presence of a diverse product assortment, the effective utilization of store floor space, and the density of the crowd all demonstrated a notable influence on consumer buying behavior at D-Mart stores in Vadodara. The study's conclusion highlighted the significant impact of these atmospheric variables on consumer purchasing behavior. In light of these findings, Munshi recommended that the store manager at D-Mart take proactive measures to enhance the shopping environment. This included paying special attention to maintaining a well-stocked product assortment, ensuring that high-demand items are consistently available on the shelves, and optimizing their display presentation. These efforts can contribute to an improved shopping experience and positively shape consumer buying behavior.

2.3.8 Mishra, et al. (2012): Impact of Physical Ambience on Communication, Collaboration and Coordination in Agile Software Development: An Empirical Evaluation

The study employed both inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis. Here are the findings and conclusions: The research revealed that half cubicles were highly effective in facilitating communication frequency. Additionally, half-height cubicles and status boards were found to be very effective in promoting coordination among team members. When it came to individual problem-solving activities and team-based work, half-height glass barriers were identified as highly effective. In summary, the physical workspace environment was recognized as playing a significant role in enhancing communication, collaboration, and coordination among individuals involved in software development. As a recommendation, the study suggests that software developers should make more effective use of open workspaces as it heightens awareness among team members, leading to improved coordination. Additionally, creating effective communal or discussion spaces can greatly aid collaboration among software developers.

2.3.9 Sabrina (2014): The Influence of the Store Atmosphere on the Consumer Behavior

The researcher examined how various components of store atmospherics impact consumer behavior and emotional responses. To analyze the data, the researcher employed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Here are the study's findings and conclusions: The research findings indicated that the characteristics of the store environment, including ambient elements and design, have a notable influence on both the actions and emotional reactions of consumers. In summary, the study concluded that store atmosphere plays a significant role in shaping consumer behavior. As a recommendation, the researcher advised that dealers, retailers, and traders should view store environments as a management tool. They can strategically utilize the store environment to positively influence the emotions of their customers and, consequently, increase the volume of their purchases.

2.3.10 Minciott, et al. (2016): Scents: Influence on Purchase Behavior in Shops in Brazil. The researchers investigated how scents affect customer purchase behavior in two similar shops. They conducted surveys and introduced scents into the shop environments. In the first week, they recorded the total number of customers without using any scents. In the second week, one shop was scented while the other was not scented. The analysis of the data was done using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Here are the key findings and conclusions: The study found that the presence of scents in the shop influenced the behavior of buyers by increasing the number of visits to the scented store. However, this increased attractiveness did not lead to higher sales in the shop. Instead, other

mediating variables such as the quality of service delivery and product quality seemed to interfere with buyer behavior. In conclusion, the researchers noted limitations in the effectiveness of scenting the shopping environment as a standalone strategy to increase sales. As a recommendation, they advised shop managers to adopt a more comprehensive perspective when considering the influence of scent on buyer behavior. Simply relying on scents may not be sufficient to increase sales or customer inclination toward purchasing specific products

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study design adopted by the researcher in this study was the survey research design. Data on the three independent variables and the dependent variable were collected from different microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design used assisted the researcher in researching out to a good number of customers of microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for the study comprises of customers of Microfinance Banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, hence the population for the study was infinite.

3.3 Sampling Technique and the Sample Size

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$N = \frac{Z^2 \times pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the z-score table.

p = 0.6 decimal (positive)

q = 0.4 decimal (negative)

e = Acceptable tolerance level of error (Stated in percentage points)

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

$$= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.6 \times 0.4)}{0.05^2}$$

$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.24}{0.0025}$$

$$= \frac{0.921984}{0.0025}$$

= 368.7

= 369

Therefore, the sample size of the study is 369. Convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for this study.

3.4 Research Instrument

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a 5 point Likert scale ranging from 5 (strongly agreed) to 1 (strongly disagree). This consisted of Section A and Section B. Section A presented respondents personal data such as the age distribution of the respondents ranging from 18 to 50 years and above, gender distribution of the respondents divided into male and female, educational level segmented into SSCE, Diploma, HND/B.Sc, Masters and Ph.D, Marital Status of the respondent made up of single, married and divorced while Section B presented questions on temperature with four questions, colour with three questions, layout and design with five questions and consumer behavior with four questions.

3.5 Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to validity test by the supervisor and other experts in the field of study. The relevance of each item in relation to the purpose of the study and the formulated hypotheses were assessed independently by the supervisor. Then the researcher used all the observation made by the supervisor and other experts in preparing the final copy of the questionnaire.

3.6 Reliability Test of the Instrument

Cronbach's Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and the obtained coefficients were;

S/N	Study Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Temperature	0.850
2	Colour	0.947
3	Layout and Design	0.831
4	Consumer Behaviour	0.875

Source: Research Data, 2022

3.6 Measures of Variables

All the physical ambience and consumer behavior variables were tapped by direct single questions.

Physical Ambience: The independent variable had been measured by different researchers using diverse construct. Patil, et al, (2021) in their study which focused on finding out the effect of store atmosphere on consumer buying behavior used the ambience such as lighting, music, scent and decoration and store layout which include artwork, furniture, size of the store and parking facility measurement was used to measure this variable. Sabrina (2014) measured it using such dimensions as music, colours and smell while Park, Lyer and Smith (1989) measured the same variable with measures such as store layout, knowledge and time pressure. Baker, Levy and Grewal (1992) used video tapes to measure ambient variables (music and lighting) and social levels (such as retail

sales people). Ndengane et al. (2021) measured with such measures such as ambient factors (flooring and displays product displays) and social factors (Store signage and Point of Sales, in-store displays and employee behavior). While Munshi (2018) measured with such measures as store floorspace, crowd density and product assortment. Yang, et al. (2022) measured this variable using visual appeal, consumer-perceived, arousal, customer engagement, interface design and live-streaming atmosphere. Hussain and Ali (2015) measured it using dimensions such as cleanliness, music, scent, temperature, lighting, colour and display/layout. The construct (Colour, temperature and design/layout) advocate by Hussain and Ali (2015) and Ndengane et al. (2021) seem consistent hence were adapted and used in this study.

Consumer Behaviour: Attintzoglou et al. (2016) in their study measured this variable using awareness, preferences and patronage. Patil et al. (2021) measured this same variable using dimensions such as emotions, cognitions, comforts and behavioural intentions (such as repurchase, positive word – of - mouth marketing and satisfaction). Hussain and Ali (2015) measured it using purchase intention. Jalil et al. (2015) measured using behavioural intention, (such as return intention positive word of mouth). Ndenyane et al. (2021) identified three constructs used in measuring this variable which were the customers pleasant mood, time spent in the store and intention to revisit the store, Hence, the construct identified by Ndengane et al. (2021) and Hussain and Ali (2015) for measuring this variable were adopted and used in this study.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Data were analyzed using the simple regression analysis to determine the effect of physical ambience on consumer behaviour of microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. All the hypotheses were tested at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

SECTION 4: DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Analysis

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of colour on customer behaviour in microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom state.

Model Summary for hypothesis one

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.847 ^a	.718	.716		2.14541

a. Predictors: (Constant), Colour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1689.225	1	1689.225	367.000	.000 ^b

Residual	662.802	144	4.603		
Total	2352.027	145			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Colour

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.897	.725		8.129	.000
	Colour	.735	.038	.847	19.157	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

The table above with R value of 0.847 indicates that there is a significant influence between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.718 implies that about 71.8% of the variation in consumer behaviour was explained by colour. The F-calculated value of 367.000 and P-value of 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. That is, the independent variable was able to explain the dependent variable very well. The constant value of 5.897 indicates that keeping independent variable (colour) constant, consumer behaviour will remain at 5.897. The coefficient of colour was 0.735 which means that a unit change in colour will lead to 0.735-unit change in consumer behaviour. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of colour on consumer behaviour was statistically significant.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of temperature on customer behaviour in microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom state

Model Summary for Hypothesis Two

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.900 ^a	.810	.808	1.76312

a. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1904.392	1	1904.392	612.625	.000 ^b
	Residual	447.635	144	3.109		

Total	2352.027	145			
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a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.686	.690		3.894	.000
	Temperature	.853	.034	.900	24.751	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

The table above with R value of 0.900 indicates that there is a significant influence between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.810 implies that about 81.0% of the variation in consumer behaviour was explained by temperature. The F-calculated value of 612.625 and P-value of 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. That is, the independent variable was able to explain the dependent variable very well. The constant value of 2.686 indicates that keeping independent variable (temperature) constant, consumer behaviour will remain at 2.686. The coefficient of temperature was 0.853 which means that a unit change in temperature will lead to 0.853 unit change in consumer behaviour. The P-value of 0.000 means that the influence of temperature on consumer behaviour was statistically significant.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: there is no significant influence of design and layout on customer behaviour in microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom state

Model Summary for Hypothesis Three

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.896 ^a	.802	.801	1.79810

a. Predictors: (Constant), Design layout

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1886.450	1	1886.450	583.466	.000 ^b
	Residual	465.578	144	3.233		
	Total	2352.027	145			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Design layout

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.918	.738		2.600	.010
	Design layout	.921	.038	.896	24.155	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior

The table above with R value of 0.896 indicates that there is a significant effect between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.802 implies that about 80.2% of the variation in consumer behaviour was explained by design layout. The F-calculated value of 583.466 and P-value of 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. That is, the independent variable was able to explain the dependent variable very well. The constant value of 1.918 indicates that keeping independent variable (design layout) constant, Consumer behaviour will remain at 1.918. The coefficient of design layout was 0.921 which means that a unit change in design layout will lead to 0.921 unit change in consumer behaviour. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of design layout on consumer behaviour was statistically significant.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The tested hypotheses were quite revealing, some validating the findings of previous scholars, others negating existing studies. The test shows that physical ambience variables such as (colour, temperature, design/layout) all had positive and significant influences on consumer behavior of microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The findings is in line with the finding of Hussain and Ali, 2015; Patil, et al; 2021; Munshi, 2018; Benat and Wanderbori, 2012; Chen and Hsieh, 2011; Sabrina, 2014; Yulsel, 2009 and Hite, 1992.

4.2.1 Temperature and Customer Behaviour in Microfinance Banks

The findings of the study showed a significant influence of temperature on consumer behavior of Microfinance Banks. The simple regression model from which F – ratio value (612.625) indicates statistical significance of the overall regression model. This was statistically significant at 0.00 because it was less than 0.05 level of significance. This is in consonance with Chen and Hsieh (2011) who found out that temperature significantly influence customer’s emotion enabling them to retain active and positive emotions including pleasant experiences.

4.2.2 Colour and Customer Behaviour in Microfinance Banks

The finding of the study revealed a significant influence of colours on consumer behavior of microfinance banks. The F-ratio in the simple regression table 4.1 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The f-ratio value is 367.000 which is significant at 0.000 and is less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance

with the findings of Chan and Hsieh (2011); Benat and Wanderbori (2012); Yulsel (2009) and Hite (1992) were of the opinion that colour greatly influence consumers' perception. They viewed red environment as unpleasant, not positive, tense and unattractive when compared to blue and green.

4.2.3 Design/Layout and Customer Behaviour in Microfinance Banks

Statistical analysis of data in table 4.3 indicated the significant influence of design/layout on consumer behavior of microfinance banks. This is in consonance with Munshi (2018); Sabrina (2014); Hussain and Ali (2015) and Patil, et al (2021). They found out that design and layout had a significant positive influence on customers when choosing banking services as it influences their actions and feelings.

SECTION 5: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The main thrusts of this study have been presented in the preceding four sections. This section is concerned with the summary of major findings. The study investigated the influence of physical ambience on consumer behavior of microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis. The three null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression result were all significant, the computed F-values for all the three hypotheses show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there are statistically significant effect of physical ambience variables such as (temperature, colour and design/display) on consumer behavior of microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objective, survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents to the banks. The population for the study was infinite. Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerance error was used to determine the sample size of 369. The convenient sampling technique was employed in the administration of research instrument for the study.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were established:

1. Temperature have significant influence on consumer behaviour of customers of microfinance banks
2. Colour have significant influence on consumer behaviour of customers of microfinance banks
3. Layout and design have significant influence on consumer behaueur of customers of microfinance banks

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the finding and conclusion of this study, we recommend that the manager of microfinance banks should enhance the efficient use of the physical ambience variables strategies to;

1. Enhance effective use of temperature in order to create a pleasant experience that is viable to influence the banks customers intention to purchase the banks service product the as aid in decision making process.
2. Enhance effective use of colour and, in order to shape as well as influence the behavior of their customers through the simulations of their senses, perception and attitudes to create desired customers reactions.

3. Design their business environment in order to produce specific value perceptions in the buyer as well as create an outstanding experience that is viable to attract and retain the banks existing and potential customers.

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